

Review

Artificial intelligence-open science symbiosis in chemoinformatics

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ABSTRACT

In chemoinformatics, artificial intelligence (AI) continues to grow a symbiosis with open science (OS). Such a close AI-OS interaction brings substantial practical benefits in research, scientific dissemination, and education, to name a few areas. The AI-OS symbiosis can be further enhanced by combining sufficient substantive expertise, mathematical and statistical knowledge, and coding skills. This Viewpoint discusses the benefits of the smooth and productive interaction between AI, OS, and open data. We also present a short list of misconceptions and pitfalls surrounding AI-OS and propose correct responses and behaviors agreed upon by field experts. In addition, we provide suggestions to continue enhancing the positive contributions of the AI-OS symbiosis towards chemoinformatics.

Background

Both theoretical and practical considerations of artificial intelligence (AI) in medicinal chemistry and chemoinformatics continue to expand at a high rate [1,2]. While AI, much through the use of machine learning (ML), has been a key component of drug discovery for the past two decades, the recent public focus on deep learning (DL) and large language models (LLMs) has brought the field even more attention. This is further aided by the large volumes of data increasingly becoming publicly accessible, largely as a publication requirement of certain scientific journals. Although many may not realize it, open science (OS), which comprises open source software and open data (OD) repositories, has been the cornerstone of AI in drug discovery. As anticipated, AI and OS form a strong synergistic cooperation which stimulates respective use and popularity, thus encouraging continued scientific development and democratization. The application of AI in chemoinformatics and drug discovery relies on three key components: data, representation, and algorithms (Fig. 1); and OS has been a major contributor of each.

Data

Reliably reported and curated data is fundamental to AI research.

Without the high-quality, task-relevant data sources it is impossible to derive accurate and robust models, irrespective of the considered data representation or algorithm. Computational life sciences as a whole considerably depend on and benefit from OD resources such as PubChem [3] and ChEMBL [4], thus their continued presence, maintenance, and support are crucial to the field's development. While current data sources are useful, a few challenges that require further attention remain. First, both chemical and associated biological data need to be harmonized and curated to enable reproducibility and robustness. Even though current chemical curation protocols [5] offer a convenient way to standardize chemical structures (e.g., neutralization, removal of salts, consistent representation, etc.), they do not, however, eliminate multiple chemical structures, remove inconsistent or beyond-the-range assay measurements, suggest how to treat truncated data (i.e., data points that are beyond the experimental detection limit, e.g., >30 μM), or perform data aggregation across multiple assays. For this, bespoke curation protocols guided by domain expertise remain relevant. Second, many widely applied benchmark data sets used to evaluate novel ML methods may lack valid and consistent representations of chemical structures and experimental measures, experimental ranges and thresholds relevant in practice, and complete stereochemistry information, to name a few. At all times, researchers are advised to evaluate and

Abbreviations: AI, artificial intelligence; DL, deep learning; DNN, deep neural network; LLM, large language model; ML, machine learning; OD, open data; OS, open science.

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Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the application of artificial intelligence in chemoinformatics and drug discovery that relies on three main pillars: data, representation, and algorithms.

further curate already published data sources (not treat ‘as is’) or to explore alternative data sets with simple, robust, relevant, and clearly defined endpoints. Several efforts to curate and clean public data sets exist and should be used whenever possible to make an informed data processing decision for a research task [6–9]. Altogether, for the field to move ahead, we require publicly funded initiatives to generate, collect, maintain, and publicly disclose high-quality data for chemoinformatics research.

Representation

To build an ML model, one needs to transform a chemical structure into a vector representation that an algorithm can process [10]. While representations are well established for other fields (e.g., pixels in image recognition or tokenized letters or words in natural language processing), representations in chemistry are still an open question. So far, the majority of the ML models have used either fingerprint representations (for example, extended-connectivity fingerprints [11] or Molecular ACCess System keys [12]) or one- and two-dimensional descriptors such as number of hydrogen bond donors or acceptors, molecular weight, and total polar surface area. Both are implemented and can conveniently be accessed through OS tools such as RDKit [13] or KNIME [14]. More recently, with the advent of learned representations via DL and deep neural networks (DNNs) came software that built on previous OS graph neural networks and convolutional neural networks from other fields. Here, OS evidently enabled other researchers to attempt to build on the methodologies with analogous representations and allowed additional benchmarking, which demonstrated methods to be roughly equivalent to the discussed fingerprints [15]. Recent popularity of LLMs has introduced new types of learned representations into chemoinformatics research. These greatly benefit from OS efforts present in the natural language processing field, as well as large volumes of text data providing the basis for transfer learning. However, the evidence for superiority (even if minimal) over conventional fingerprint designs and ML methods is typically scarce and less significant than initially reported [16]. However, the LLM research in medicinal chemistry is increasing, and further monitoring of benefits and disadvantages is required. On the other hand, researchers still need to figure out how to best utilize

three-dimensional information, as this issue is not limited to representation only but also suitable algorithms and computational resources.

Algorithms

Finally, ML algorithms aim to establish a relationship between the representation and an assigned label (in the case of supervised learning) which, depending on the task at hand, can either be a regression or a classification. The catalyst for the current surge of ML in quantitative structure-activity relationship tasks is a research paper by Svetnik et al., which introduced random forest as both a regression and a classification algorithm, described together with a fully accessible R code [17]. Currently, several OS implementations of ML algorithms exist, such as Scikit learn [18], containing more traditional ML methods, and Pytorch [19] and TensorFlow [20], which focus on DL algorithms. Important to note is that these resources highly depend on a dedicated group of developers but also contributors from the community, which is a model that will need to be maintained going forward.

The goal of this Viewpoint is to discuss the advantages, including a short list of misconceptions and pitfalls with proposed correct responses, of currently available AI tools, OS resources, and their practices. In addition, it aims to healthily encourage the OS initiative and its practical use in AI for chemoinformatics applications while simultaneously limiting the overpromotion of unrealistic, insufficiently validated, and sometimes misused methods and results. By its very nature, this Viewpoint is partly subjective and does not comprehensively capture all the best practices and malpractices or misuses; instead, we wish to stimulate an open and continued discussion with the scientific community and, most importantly, draw their attention to the benefits and issues currently present in the AI-OS space.

Artificial intelligence in chemoinformatics and medicinal chemistry

AI in chemoinformatics and medicinal chemistry currently considers only a fragment of disciplines available from the field of computer sciences. Among these, ML and DL, and -to a lesser extent- robotics, account for the majority of study cases, whereas the other AI approaches including expert and recommender systems are yet to be appreciably considered [21]. Currently, many research studies explore DL and associated DNNs for molecular property prediction tasks. These commonly consider predefined molecular representations and tabular data sets that are smaller in sizes compared to other research areas where DL has gathered considerable success, such as natural language processing or image recognition [22]. Therefore, it is not surprising that, thus far, DL has not been able to demonstrate considerable improvement in predictive performance compared to more traditional ML approaches, such as the random forest or support vector machines [22]. In part, this may be because DL methods typically employ a learned representation which requires large data sets to develop. Even though AI has been present in chemoinformatics for the past several decades, and continues to expand with the ever-increasing computational power, the adoption of novel AI methodologies has been mostly steady so far, in part influenced by moderate developments in related experimental fields, such as chemical biology and medicinal chemistry, including the chemical synthesis of large and ultra-large chemical libraries [23]. For instance, progress on structure-based and AI-based computational screening of ultra-large chemical libraries and the subsequent data deposition in public databases such as PubChem [3] and ChEMBL [4] facilitate the generation of predictive models. However, the rate-limiting step of this process remains the synthesis of diverse chemical libraries that require bespoke synthesis protocols, each amounting to several weeks (or even months) worth of labor.

However, more often than not, a sudden and rapid increase in usage and popularity of novel open-source AI systems elsewhere (e.g., LLMs in the form of recently developed chatbots) triggers practitioners, and

others alike, to utilize these novel developments to answer research questions analogous to those found in the original reports. The adoption of novel technologies typically requires distinct expertise and significant effort. Thus, such methods are commonly introduced by researchers whose prowess is concerned with the questioned algorithm(s). However, even if the application of novel methodologies is technically correct, there is a risk of using flawed benchmark data sets to demonstrate performance or of incompletely (or even incorrectly) performing statistical evaluation, among other issues. On the other hand, traditional computational chemists may need more knowledge to understand and apply new algorithms. Both of these instances may give rise to suboptimal research, which suggests that research and application scientists with expertise in different areas (e.g., computer science and medicinal chemistry) should collaborate closely to ensure the proper use of novel AI technologies. Since medicinal chemistry and chemoinformatics, much like other research areas, are not immune to the fashion and hype associated with AI, examples of poor practices may quickly evolve into misuses [24] or applications with limited benefit. This applies even to well-established AI methods, such as the traditional ML or DL, where the number of insufficiently validated research studies is on the rise.

Open science

OS has been defined as “transparent and accessible knowledge that is shared and developed through collaborative networks” [25]. OS includes OD and open source code and software, impacting favorably several areas as detailed in the following (Fig. 2).

The OS culture has grown significantly, promising to accelerate existing efforts to disseminate data and tools among academics and industrial scientists [26]. In turn, such a trend ensures access to valuable data sources and advanced technologies, ease of reproducibility of published research, and introduction (and inclusion) of non-experts to the field (Fig. 2). Advances in free storage platforms such as GitHub, Zenodo, Figshare, and others contribute to the ease of data, code, and

tool sharing. Moreover, preprint servers such as bioRxiv, ChemRxiv, and arXiv enable researchers to share the final versions of their peer-reviewed papers if the journals are behind the paywall, or to disclose accepted conference papers that would normally be absent from the public domain. For example, ML framework reports that are now widely used in chemoinformatics research, such as Pytorch [19] and TensorFlow [20], have initially been published on the preprint servers. In this regard, OS largely contributes to the democratization of science, facilitating the practice, teaching, and contribution to research by research groups worldwide, including low- and middle-income countries whose access to commercial software and (expensive) data resources may be limited (Fig. 2). Similarly, the continued (and increased) hardship in obtaining grants to secure the sustained acquisition of software licenses and other commercial data sources, such as databases, also stresses the relevance of having access to quality open access resources. This applies not only to low-/middle-income countries but also to high-income countries where strong competition exists to obtain research grants.

AI-OS symbiosis: the goods

Given their interdependence in a practical setting, the AI-OS collaboration became a natural next step – AI algorithms require large volumes of public data to derive potentially valuable insights and prove their worth, whereas OS grows from the development and transferability of, among others, AI methodological frameworks. Altogether, positive efforts found in AI and OS spaces contribute to the further development of the chemoinformatics field, grow its capabilities, and expand the responsibilities and contributions of computational life scientists.

Currently, some peer-reviewed journals focused on computational approaches are making it mandatory to make open access to the raw data, code, and results as a requisite for publication [27–29]. However, it is necessary that other journals join this effort. Since peer-reviewed publications are still a significant component in academic institutions

Fig. 2. Open science (OS) impacts different areas and levels, including data, technology, methodology, and the democratization of science. OS benefits dissemination, sharing, accessibility, introduction, and inclusion of non-experts, and favors reproducibility of published research. Democratization of science influences the practice, teaching, and tool sharing in the community at large.

as a criterion of performance and productivity (hence funding), there is pressure to develop open-source applications. In turn, research groups need to get funds, usually through research grants, to maintain, update, and improve free resources (e.g., websites and predictive models) developed based on public data such as ChEMBL [4] and PubChem [3]. For example, ChEMBL is updated regularly, but published predictive models developed on previous versions of this database become outdated rapidly (and eventually obsolete) over time. In such cases, the user of the models developed with previous versions of databases such as ChEMBL and PubChem should be aware of their applicability domain. Similarly, several public compound databases and chemoinformatics tools are no longer available because of the need for more funding to maintain and update these resources [30,31].

Frequently updated OD and OS sources are particularly important to low- and middle-income country researchers who largely base their efforts on such resources. Given the particularity of their research, which commonly focuses on diseases typical to their geographic origin (e.g., malaria, leishmaniasis, Chagas disease, etc.), they almost entirely depend on OD databases that contain contributions from large academic laboratories, institutes, and pharmaceutical companies. For example, ChEMBL [4] features a ChEMBL-NTD repository that assembles medicinal chemistry and primary screening data directed at neglected tropical diseases present in developing regions of Africa, Asia, and the Americas. Similarly, ChEMBL features a malaria inhibitor prediction platform that is intended for predicting blood stage malaria inhibition. As common with OD initiatives, no funding from commercial organizations, individuals, or investors are received, which makes these data collections reliant on public contributions. Clearly, for disease research areas focal to low- and middle-income country researchers, there exists a high unmet need that considerably depends on an altruistic but fragile OS interconnection.

In this regard, large pharmaceutical and software companies continue to be major benefactors of AI-OS growth by open-sourcing their data and research. For example, although the majority of chemical and biological data still remains proprietary to this day, pharmaceutical industry frequently discloses information from (most commonly) closed medicinal chemistry projects in the form of research publications and patent applications, or commits resources to OS initiatives and consortia. Equally, PyTorch [19] and TensorFlow [20], two of the most popular ML frameworks, were developed by Meta AI (now part of the Linux Foundation) and Google Brain, respectively. Without these (and particularly the latter), the application of novel AI methodologies in medicinal chemistry, and beyond, could never be imagined. As expected, the levels of OD sharing are disproportionate, where the pharmaceutical industry is the more conservative of the two, which can be partly ascribed to the cultural differences present in these environments. Compared to several decades ago, however, it is apparent that the culture in pharmaceutical companies has been steadily shifting towards OS, mainly through publication efforts but also disclosed data and software.

The most evident manifestation of AI-OS cooperation is the community contribution to the OS code and methodological development that benefits research groups worldwide. While the authors are responsible for the code deposition, documentation, and authenticity (according to research claims), the community members ultimately evaluate and use code in their research. Their continuous support greatly benefits further improvement and implementation of OS tools, often beyond any official code releases or publication reports. For example, RDKit [13] is among the major OS chemoinformatics resources that owes its existence to the community members who frequently report concerns, propose code modifications, or indicate novel developments that could be added to the framework. Equally, RDKit eases implementation of chemoinformatics and ML tools, thus accelerating research and work. Moreover, without OS, the initial transition and transformation of many AI methodological approaches from other fields into chemoinformatics would not be possible. Therefore, an uninterrupted collaboration among the code developers will remain critical to

the evolution of many AI research tools.

Another positive interplay of AI-OS that benefits research and education are the many blogs maintained by influential life scientists who discuss and evaluate the latest developments, provide exemplary use cases or statistical methods to assess known chemoinformatics or bioinformatics frameworks, or publicly deposit educational material through OS code or Jupyter notebooks [32–34]. Both the informal narrating style and step-by-step guidance make these resources highly attractive, especially to early career researchers. Therefore, it is not uncommon that these AI-OS-mediated interactions bring researchers together short-term to develop novel methodological approaches but also long-term through joint research grants and shared (post)doctoral candidates. Evidently, resourcefulness and inclusivity are the backbone of chemoinformatics research and here AI-OS collaboration plays a major role in connecting researchers that often come from different institutions and geographical regions.

AI-OS: the warnings

However, as it often happens, much of the hype surrounding AI has not bypassed chemoinformatics, and threatens to damage its credibility, often through unrealistic expectations or potential misguidance of more traditional, experimental fields such as medicinal chemistry and chemical biology [35]. Thus, the broad and natural benefits of the AI-OS symbiosis are not free from misconceptions and malpractices briefly presented in this section.

First part of Table 1 discusses misconceptions, as well as misleading statements and concepts, attributed to the application and development of AI-OS resources. These misconceptions are typically associated with uneducated, uninformed, or unrealistic views of promises and achievements accumulated in the AI-OS space present in other research fields that were later introduced to chemoinformatics. Second part of Table 1 summarizes a few representative pitfalls and malpractices present among the practitioners. Both parts are counterbalanced by potential correct responses and behaviors with a more healthy and realistic perspective of the AI-OS collaboration. Although not extensive, the proposed list of misconceptions and pitfalls (including associated responses) aims to provide practitioners and early career researchers with a reference checklist to evaluate and potentially correct their positioning towards the existing and coming developments in the AI-OS space. We state the author's opinion for each misconception and pitfall, including proposed corrective behavior or response.

Closing remarks

AI is becoming increasingly applied in medicinal chemistry and chemoinformatics research, mainly by adopting existing computer science methodologies. On their own, OS and OD have enormous potential to accelerate the dissemination of data and tools among academic and industrial scientists. Undoubtedly, in practice, AI and OS form an interdependent relationship with many positive outcomes, such as contribution to the scientific democratization through data, software, and model sharing; moreover, AI-OS synergy impacts education and funding at different levels. However, as common with popular technologies, misconceptions and misuses can harm the intended benefits of AI-OS symbiosis.

We envision that there are a number of critical areas of opportunity to advance the field further. In terms of data, high-quality, up-to-date public data sets are required for model training and validation. While proposing new or improved algorithms, it is anticipated that the community will improve the statistical rigor in methods comparison. To these ends, editorial and scientific advisory board members could help to establish, refine, maintain, and enforce guidelines for researchers to deposit and share high-quality data, algorithms, and models in the public domain. Here, for example, the authors should be encouraged to publish negative data (e.g., compounds displaying inactivity in

Table 1

Examples of misconceptions (first part) and pitfalls (second part) that could affect the AI-OS interaction, including potential correct responses and corrections, respectively.

Misconceptions	Correct responses agreed among field experts
Data published in OD databases should not be questioned and can be freely used and combined.	OD sources may still contain erroneous experimental data. Thus, further evaluation, curation, and (if needed) aggregation of OD resources is required prior to any conducted modeling exercise. For this, bespoke curation protocols guided by domain expertise continue to be relevant. Rigorous and detailed investigation must be conducted prior to any computational experiment [6]. This includes the use of many widely applied benchmark data sets which contain additional errors to those adopted from original OD sources: incorrect chemical structures, invalid aggregated measurements, to name a few; often overlooked by the modelers. In addition, OD many times lacks negative data that is relevant to develop predictive models [36].
Data and codes published open access in preprints are as valid as peer-reviewed articles.	Findings presented in preprints should be treated with caution as their content may further evolve or be rejected due to invalidated experiments [37]. However, in certain cases such as the published articles being behind the paywall of journals or accepted to conferences, the peer-reviewed version of the manuscript/presentation may also be found on preprint servers. Similarly, peer-reviewed versions of articles, including supplementary data and models, may also (although to a lesser extent) contain invalid claims because journal reviewers and editors often do not validate them in practice.
As long as my data/models are publicly available, that is called OD.	While this constitutes the notion of OD, it is not a sole defining factor. Rather, the data should be well described stating the experimental conditions, providing all the replicates and not only the final averaged values, in order to ensure that the approximation of experimental errors can later be used in estimating model usability. As for the models, these should be fully executable in a free-of-charge manner to ensure reproducibility [26].
Public data/tools are the only major contributors to the advancement of science; hence, all should be made public and with no restrictions.	While OD and tools, if properly documented and shared, are significant contributors to advancing AI in chemoinformatics, they are not the only option. For decades, private companies have been and continue to be major generators and developers of concepts/tools/resources that benefit society. Profits or earnings generated by private institutions help to sustain the development and maintenance of the resources. Also, while scientific data that represents a benefit for society should be made public, data and tools that can be potentially misused, should be restricted and kept confidential [38].
Pitfalls	Corrections
Any 'new, free, and cool AI' open access tool used almost immediately to claim own's pioneering position in drug discovery.	While novel open access technologies are intriguing, their use in scientific research should still be conducted in a rigorous manner. Applicability of novel AI tools to particular research cases should be (in)validated through a series of unbiased experiments [24].
AI tools and predictive models, in general, gain the most value if implemented in free web servers that are easy to use where the user can get a fast response/results.	Before using the free server and the data to make decisions, the user must be trained on the basics used to develop the models and their limitations. The proper training must be informed depending on the level/type of the decisions taken with the data.
Data or computational tools are shared partially: the release is incomplete or, after the release was done (e.g., paper published), the data/tools are withdrawn from public access.	The authors who provide access to their data/tools need to ensure that the shared information about their data is complete (e.g., adequately described standard operating procedures stating the assay conditions and individual replicate records that can later be applied to estimate experimental errors), that control calculations are implemented to evaluate the model's usefulness (e.g., comparison against experimental errors, dummy models, and sufficient increase in performance or at least benefit in particular data cases when compared to similar models to declare eventual success/advantage).

biological assays) as this would help decreasing the categorical imbalance (e.g., active versus inactive) present in the public domain, which would allow for building better and more informative AI models [39]. Traditionally, negative data are perceived as irrelevant to the general understanding of medicinal chemistry community (i.e., scientific reports typically discuss optimization efforts towards drugs with better biological and pharmacokinetic profiles), yet for AI-based applications negative data could be as equally important as the published positive data. From a technical point of view, it will be necessary to develop and maintain novel public repositories to share data and code, thus facilitating transformation of data into relevant information, and further into knowledge. For example, large databases annotated with biological data such as ChEMBL [4] and PubChem [3] could help the implementation and maintenance of AI-based models to predict biological endpoints using high-quality data. One area where this would be of great practical value are the neglected tropical diseases (and other research areas specific to low- and middle-income countries) which currently heavily depend on OD resources and public contributions. We also expect that the community will continue to play a vital role in evaluating, refining, distributing, and maintaining OS resources, as well as educational material that will remain particularly relevant to early career researchers with no or limited access to free or formal education. Much like in the code development space, the community should actively participate in curating relevant and challenging benchmarking data sets (and continue

to develop the established ones). In this regard, competitions such as CASP (Critical Assessment of Structure Prediction) [40] and CACHE (Critical Assessment of Computational Hit-finding Experiments) [41] have advanced protein structure and computational hit-finding predictions, respectively. Therefore, there is an expectation that an increased presence of similar challenges will foster further development of areas where researchers are met with significant scientific hurdles.

In light of this, and driven by the increased need for highly-trained professionals, it is anticipated that an increased number of academic programs at the interface of different areas, such as coding, statistical, and domain (medicinal chemistry, life sciences, etc.) knowledge, will become increasingly available and accessible over time. We expect that the present Viewpoint will contribute towards reflecting and keeping the discussion with the scientific community open, thus strengthening the benefits of AI-OS collaboration to advance medicinal and computational chemistry further.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Filip Miljković: Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **José L. Medina-Franco:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that there are no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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